

Chemistry of Blue Chromium Peroxide Adducts with Ketoanils

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Peroxy derivatives of transition metals are of growing importance in relation to catalysis of oxidations, storage and use of oxygen in biological systems. Their adducts with electron-pair donor organics, including products of blue chromium peroxide and amines, being easily isolated owing to their enhanced stability, have been frequently studied¹ for their structures and properties. Blue chromium peroxide adducts with ketoanils, have been described in the present communication.

Results and Discussion

Stoichiometry of the adducts (Table 1) corresponds to their analytical data. Water molecules seem to be coordinated² with the metal as IR spectra of the adducts display twisting, wagging and rocking vibrations at around 984 and ~ 836 cm⁻¹, and M-O stretch at 290-395 cm⁻¹. The

bands at 3 050-3 310 and 1 585-1 640 cm⁻¹ attributable² to symmetric and antisymmetric stretching and bending vibrations of lattice water, indicate the presence of water of crystallisation except compounds of serial number 8 and 10 (Table 1) though stretching vibrations of C=N and/or C=O (quinonoid) or C=C (aromatic) and intramolecularly bonded O-H groups also occur in the same regions.

Considerable lowering in $\nu_{C=N}$ band of the ketoanils on complexation (~1 638 to ~1 603 cm⁻¹) indicates coordination of azomethine group of the ligands with chromium. A new band at ~521 cm⁻¹ (Cr-N) in the spectra of the adducts supports this inference. Undisturbed positions of δ_{OH} (~1 035, ~1 193), $\nu_{C=O}$ (phenolic and enolic) (~1 256), ν_{OH} (2 638, ~3 145, ~3 290), and $\nu_{C=O}$ (~1 692 cm⁻¹) bands of the ketoanils during complexation, however, to-

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF THE ADDUCTS*

Sl. no	Compd. (R = C ₆ H ₄ OH/ Colour)	M.p. (°C)	μ_{eff} (Debye)		10 Dg cm ⁻¹	B cm ⁻¹	ν cm ⁻¹	β	LFSE cm ⁻¹
			(Electrolytic nature)	B.M.					
1	Cr ₃ O ₈ (R-C ₅ H ₄ N-o) ₆ .9H ₂ O (Chocolate)	>175 ^a	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
2	Cr ₃ O ₈ (R-C ₆ H ₄ SH-o) ₃ .8H ₂ O (Black)	172 ^a	178.0 (1 : 1)	3.56	16 949	553	2 046	0.54	20 334
3	Cr ₃ O ₈ (R-C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -o) ₃ .10H ₂ O (Yellow)	200 ^a	94.6 (1 : 1)	3.84	17 857	636	2 357	0.62	21 428
4	Cr ₃ O ₈ (R-C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -m) ₆ .9H ₂ O (Chocolate)	160 ^a	118.1 (1 : 1)	3.82	16 807	637	2 357	0.52	20 168
5	Cr ₃ O ₈ (R-C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -p) ₆ .8H ₂ O (Green)	138 ^b	126.0 (1 : 1)	3.76	17 057	757	2 801	0.73	21 428
6	Cr ₃ O ₈ (R-C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃ -o) ₃ .12H ₂ O (Black)	240 ^a	04.6 ^c	3.54	16 667	693	2 564	0.67	20 000
7	Cr ₃ O ₈ (R-C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃ -p) ₆ .3H ₂ O (Brown)	205 ^a	108.9 (1 : 1)	-	16 667	733	2 712	0.71	20 000
8	Cr ₃ O ₈ (R-C ₆ H ₄ N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂ -p) ₆ .2H ₂ O (Green)	150	109.7 (1 : 1)	3.56	16 393	698	2 583	0.68	19 672
9	Cr ₃ O ₈ (R-C ₆ H ₄ R-p) ₃ .9H ₂ O (Green)	250 ^a	102.7 (1 : 1)	3.87	17 241	724	2 679	0.70	20 689
10	Cr ₃ O ₈ (R-C ₆ H ₄ C ₆ H ₄ -R-p) ₄ .4H ₂ O (Brown)	>320	139.5 (1 : 1)	-	-	-	-	-	-
11	Cr ₃ O ₈ (R-CH ₂ CH ₂ -R) ₃ .11H ₂ O (Brown)	250 ^a	95.4 (1 : 1)	3.55	16 949	689	2 549	0.67	20 339
12	(Cr ₃ O ₈) ₂ (R-CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂ -R-1.3) ₆ .12H ₂ O (Brown)	182 ^b	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

^aDecomposed. ^bSwelled. ^cNon-electrolyte.

tally rules out coordination of C=O and OH groups of the ligands. Molar conductance values reveal³ 1 : 1 electrolytic nature of the adducts. These values indicate decomposition of blue chromium peroxy compound to chromium(III) peroxychromate by ketoanils during their coordination along with water molecules with Cr^{III} ions bridged by peroxy groups. Peroxy-bridged structure of the adducts gets support from the characteristic ir band at ~885 cm⁻¹. General structure of adducts may be proposed as [Cr^{III}(O₂)(H₂O)_nL_n]CrO₄ (n = 2, 3, 4, or 6; L = ketoanil)

Magnetic moments of adducts, close to spin-only value of Cr^{III} ion in octahedral field, indicate their high-spin octahedral stereochemistry⁴. Electronic spectra, displaying 3-5 ligand field bands at ~13 987, ~15 329, ~17 043, ~23 831 and ~39 229 cm⁻¹ attributable to *d-d* transitions from ⁴A_{2g}(F) ground state to ²E_g, ²T_{1g}, ⁴T_{2g}(F), ⁴T_{1g}(F) and ⁴T_{1g}(P) excited states respectively, are consistent with magnetic measurement results. Ligand field parameters were calculated⁵. The values of magnetic moment (μ_{eff}), 10Dq, Racah's parameters (B and C), nephelauxetic ratio (β) and LFSE are presented in Table 1. In addition to ligand field bands, one or two bands of ligand-to-metal charge transfer with high intensity have been observed at ~41 511 and ~44 444 cm⁻¹.

Experimental

For the synthesis of ketoanils, a mixture of saturated solutions of *o*-hydroxyphenylglyoxal (0.03 mol) and an amine (monoamine, 0.03 mol and diamine, 0.015 mol) in ether were stirred at room temperature. The resulting ketoanils precipitated either immediately or after some time, were washed with ether and crystallised from benzene, acetone, chloroform or alcohol. *o*-Hydroxyphenyl-

glyoxal was obtained by the oxidation of *o*-hydroxyacetophenone with selenium dioxide following the reported method⁶.

On mixing freshly prepared solutions of blue chromium peroxide (0.01 mol) and ketoanil (0.02 mol) in ether, the adducts were precipitated immediately or were obtained as residue after complete evaporation of solvent on a water bath. The products were washed with ether to remove excess ketoanil, if any, and dried in a air-oven at ~50°.

M.ps.were determined in open glass capillaries and are uncorrected. C, H and N were estimated microanalytically. Conductance of the complexes (in DMF) was measured on a Toshniwal conductivity bridge using a dip-type cell. Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer-577 spectrophotometer and reflectance spectra (MgO) of the pulverised adducts on a VSU-2P spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibility of the powdered solid was measured on a vibrational magnetometer.

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References

1. H. J. EMELEBUS and A. G. SHARPE, "Advances in Inorganic Chemistry and Radiochemistry", Academic, New York, 1964.
2. J. LEWIS and R. G. WILKINS, "Modern Coordination Chemistry", Interscience, New York, 1964.
3. M. VERMA, Ph.D. Thesis, Meerut University, 1993.
4. D. F. HANSEN, M. C. CORMIC and D. X. WEST, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1977, **39**, 2086; D. W. MECK, R. S. DRAGE and T. S. PIPER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, **1**, 285.
5. E. KONIG, *Struct. Bonding*, 1971, **9**.
6. R. K. UPADHYAY, N. AGARWAL and N. GUPTA, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1991, **542**, 531.